

Horizon 2020
Programme

Clearing House

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

This project has received funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
under grant agreement No 821242

Start date : 2019-09-01 Duration : 48 Months
<http://clearinghouseproject.eu>

Sino-European co-design report

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Clearing House - Contract Number: 821242

Project officer: Sofie VANDEWOESTIJNE

Document title	Sino-European co-design report
Author(s)	Dr. Rik DE VREESE, WHITTLESEY S. (LGI), BIAZ L. (LGI), SCHANTE J. (LGI)
Number of pages	0
Document type	Deliverable
Work Package	WP3
Document number	D3.3
Issued by	EFI
Date of completion	2022-01-07 10:57:44
Dissemination level	Public

Summary

This report summarizes the results of the Sino-European co-design event, which was organized as part of Task 3.1 in the CLEARING HOUSE project. The event took place virtually in two parts, on June 14th and June 25th, 2021, and was organized by CAF-RIF and EFI, with the support of LGI. The events brought together cities, policymakers, civil society and scientists from all selected case studies and relevant continental organisations in Europe and China. It had two main objectives. Part one sought to identify the most critical questions to be analysed in the comparative case study analysis (T2.2). Meanwhile part two focused on defining the requirements for the tools and actions to be developed during WP4 and WP5, so that the implementation of CLEARING HOUSE can respond to multiple stakeholders' needs in the best possible manner. The core outcomes of these events, which are documented in this co-design report, will be decisive to inform the analytical framework for the case study analysis

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Project CLEARING HOUSE

Deliverable D3.3

Sino-European Co-design Report

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December 2021

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS	2
Tables	2
Figures	2
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
KEYWORDS	3
1 INTRODUCTION	4
1.1 Participation	4
1.2 Objective and Methodology of the Workshop.....	5
2 Results from Workshop Part 1	10
3 Results from Workshop Part 2	17
CONCLUSION	26
ANNEX	26

Annex

Tables

<i>Table 1: Key Questions</i>	11
<i>Table 2: Research Priorities</i>	13
<i>Table 3: Investigative Approach</i>	14
<i>Table 4: Expected Outputs</i>	16
<i>Table 5: Task T4.1 - Urban Forests as Nature-Based Solutions (UF-NBS) Business Models and Investment Cases</i>	17
<i>Table 6: Task T4.2 - Urban Forests as Nature-Based Solutions Tools Development</i>	19
<i>Table 7: Task T4.3 - Thematic Guidelines</i>	22
<i>Table 8: Task T4.4- Field Laboratories</i>	24
<i>Table 9: Task 5.3 Maintaining a webinar platform for knowledge exchange and upskilling</i>	25

Figures

<i>Figure 1: Workshop participants on June 25th</i>	4
<i>Figure 2: Workshop participants on June 25th – continued</i>	5
<i>Figure 3: Task 3.1 planning</i>	5
<i>Figure 4: Extract from the UF-NBS typology</i>	6
<i>Figure 5: Task T5.5 Innovation Roadmap</i>	26

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

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KEYWORDS

Urban forests, nature-based solutions, Sustainable urban development, trees, biodiversity, urban regeneration, codesign

1 INTRODUCTION

The Workshop Internal Report synthesizes the results of the Sino-EU Codesign Workshops held virtually on June 14th and June 25th, 2021. This report is intended to document the core outcomes of these events to help inform the analytical framework for the case study analysis.

1.1 Participation

A wide variety of stakeholders representing a diversity of positions in the public, non-profit and private sector in both Europe and China took part in the workshop. Fifty-four participants registered for part one of the workshop, and seventy-one attended part two. The many institutions that took part included: the European Forest Institute, Beijing Forestry University, the International Union for the Conservation of Nature, the Chinese Academy of Forestry, LGI Sustainable Innovation, the City of Krakow, the University of Hong Kong, Newcastle University, Free University of Brussels, Humboldt University Berlin, the city of Gelsenkirchen, the city of Guangzhou, Barcelona Metropolitan Area, the Sendzimir Foundation, Fujian Agricultural and Forestry University, as well as others. Photos (taken with consent) of attendees for part one of the workshop can be found below.

Figure 1: Workshop participants on June 25th

Figure 2: Workshop participants on June 25th – continued

1.2 Objective and Methodology of the Workshop

The Sino-EU codesign workshop was organized within Task 3.1 of CLEARING HOUSE, which seeks to implement the co-design and co-learning processes within the 10 case study cities (5 in Europe and 5 in China). The event was a central aspect of Task 3.1, as can be visualized in *Figure 3* below. It builds upon initial findings from the local workshops held in all project cities and will feed into a further round of two co-learning stakeholder workshop series. The final results of the co-creation workshop murals are available in the annex of this report.

Figure 3: Task 3.1 planning

Part one of the Sino-EU codesign workshop

The first workshop took place virtually on June 14th 2021. It builds upon the work carried out in WP1 of CLEARING HOUSE and sought to inform the analytical framework for the case study analysis, to be developed in T1.5. It had the objective of **promoting international dialogue on the most critical questions to be analysed in the comparative case study analysis (T2.2) for the implementation of urban forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS) across Europe and China.**

The event began with a presentation by Dagmar Haase of the key results that have emerged from the research carried out in WP1. Her presentation emphasized the work conducted in Tasks 1.1, 1.2, 1.4 and 1.5.

Task 1.1 focuses on identifying and mapping UF-NBS and developing a typology. The task has implemented a typology that expresses UF-NBS through “building blocks” and their relationships (e.g., single tree and tree a group of trees adjacent to a street as the outcome of a greening action)

- The **technical-methodological advancement** of this task has built knowledge for *reasoning and inference* in order to:
 - allow building of **UF-NBS inventories**
 - provide anchor points for **integration and linking of models and tree databases**, e.g., iTree or CiTree
 - facilitate **development of knowledge-based decision support systems**

Figure 4: Extract from the UF-NBS typology

Task 1.2 is researching UF-NBS practices in Europe and China. The key takeaways from this task are:

- UF-NBS offer a wide range of benefits through ecosystem services
- Sound strategic planning has shown to be key in successful UF-NBS implementation
- Planning tools and fundraising campaigns can be made broadly inclusive

- Mapping tools help demonstrate the benefits of afforestation on health and wellbeing
- Norms and guidelines should relate to a knowledge base
- Enhancing and restoring ecosystem services and biodiversity was found to form the basis of all successful UF-NBS implementations.
- Strong emphasis in the Chinese case histories on reforestation and conservation alongside reconnecting ecological corridors, reducing the heat island effect, and protecting indigenous tree species along with the relationship to wetlands.

Meanwhile, Task 1.4 is dedicated to studying governance schemes. Five key governance recommendations were presented based on the findings of this task:

1. This investigation of governance, institutional and economic frameworks has revealed significant opportunities for future research.
2. In both continents a process of reflection and mutual learning is needed to enhance the role of citizens in UF-NBS.
3. Those involved in funding decisions should ensure that long-term management after implementation is fully accounted for in project planning.
4. Mechanisms for the engagement of non-governmental sources of funding need to be fully understood and enhanced if the private sector and other means of securing resources are to be successfully applied.
5. Europe does not have a direct equivalent of the Chinese Forest Cities → Europe can learn from this and institute a culturally appropriate equivalent and learn from China's key performance indicators.

The final task from WP1 that was presented was T1.5, which aims at co-creating a starting point for our analytical framework for UF-NBS. The guiding questions for analytical framework development with case study representatives and practitioners were also presented as follows:

- What do you want to get from your urban forestry or tree-based nature-based solutions (UF-NBS)?
- What do you see as success factor(s) of your UF-NBS?
- Is biodiversity a primary aim when implementing UF-NBS?
- When would you say the UF-NBS failed?
- Do you have information of the costs of the UF-NBS and the benefits?
- Is budget a supporting or hindering factor for UF-NBS implementation?
- Are budgets available for new or restored UF-NBS?
- Is budget available for managing UF-NBS?
- Who participated in the creation of the UF-NBS in your case?
- Is a broad participation a supporting or a hindering factor?

Based on the research from WP1, four key themes emerged where cross-case study comparison appeared particularly useful. The four key areas for investigative research were: **Governance, Knowledge & Indicators, Business & Management models, and Multifunctionalities & Dilemmas**. In the following portion of the workshop participants were invited to split into three group discussions, which were facilitated using the interactive online platform, Mural. Each group discussions targeted different elements of the four key research areas.

Each of the three discussion groups was invited to first spend 25 minutes proposing the **key research questions related to the four areas of research**. The goal here was to elaborate overarching research questions related to UF-NBS, while also providing sub-questions that could help clarify the research direction. Participants were then asked to narrow their scope and prioritize only a few key research areas, both for the entire CLEARING HOUSE project and for individual cities they were familiar with.

Next, participants were asked to propose suitable **investigative approaches to conduct research** into stated research questions. The ambition here was to provide concrete approaches for conducting research and gathering data about UF-NBS related issues. Breakout discussions then concluded by asking participants to list their expected outputs for the research done in T2.2. All workshop participants were then asked to regroup for a final presentation of the day's brainstorming activities and a concluding presentation by Professor Wang.

Part 2 of the workshop

The second workshop then took place virtually on June 25th, 2021. Its objective was to **define the requirements for the tools and actions to be developed during WP4 and WP5**, so that the implementation of CLEARING HOUSE responds to multiple stakeholders' needs in the best possible manner.

The workshop started by an introduction to the different tasks of WP4 and WP5 and then a presentation by CAF-RIF about UF-NBS sustainable business models used in China and by Chinese UAG about existing examples of local UF-NBS. In a nutshell, the following elements were presented:

- UF-NBS sustainable business models in China: There are several financing models in China among which, 100% government revenue (e.g. Beijing Afforestation Project) and government-oriented/coordinate models (e.g. Green Lungs of City Project or Meishan Dongpo Urban Wetland Park).
 - Green Lungs of City Project financial model is **Public-Private**: the local government launched the project, and opened a tendering for selecting one or more companies. The authorized company has the rights to invest and implement the project on a long period. When the concession duration ends, the company needs to return the project to the government and the related departments or bureaus will do the future maintenance.
 - Meishan Dongpo Urban Wetland Park financial model is a **Resource-Compensate-Project mode**: the government will give the special rights for contractors and allow them to implement the project (planning, design, construction, management) at a specific duration. After the concession period, the authorized investors should return the project to the government.
- Chinese government projects have strict procedures:
 - The government launches the project and opens a tender for public
 - The organization that wins the tender will develop the planning draft
 - Different stakeholders join the review process of the planning but usually, they don't put all stakeholders at the same table to avoid conflicts. Stakeholders include:
 - Related government department (roads, water, etc.)

- Scientists (landscape ecology, urban planning, biodiversity, etc.)
- Public feedback (the plan will post on the official website and wait for citizens' feedback)
- Existing examples of local UF-NBS presented by Chinese UAG:
 - Presentation of a project in Shenzhen which aimed to research and test types of trees able to resist typhon and protect the city from climate hazards,
 - Presentation of a carbon capture city which planted over 100,000 trees and a 40km airport road of beautiful flowers,
 - Presentation of a rural reforestation project to align with a national plan to have a beautiful countryside and encourage citizens to go to countryside and enjoy their environmental right

2 Results from Workshop Part 1

Step 1: Key research questions related to the four areas of research

The breakout groups began participating in the first day of workshops by raising the key questions pertaining to the four cross cutting themes relating to T2.2. The results of participants' input can be seen in *Table 1* below. For all tables of results, points listed in red were initially written in Mandarin and translated for this report. The discussion about key questions provided a wide range of interesting dialogue, that highlights the breadth and complexity of implementing UF-NBS.

Within each of the subtopics, several overarching themes tended to emerge. Proposals of key questions within the governance discussion can be grouped into several sub-topics. Many participants proposed questions related to the **most appropriate model of governance for UF-NBS**. These tended to emphasize issues relating to what scale is the most appropriate to govern UF-NBS (e.g., metropolitan) as well as issues relating to stakeholder inclusion. Participants also raised several key questions related to **land and ecosystem management**, including questions of spatial planning. Another group of key questions relates to **pedagogy surrounding UF-NBS**, particularly the way that the general public and policy makers should be educated about ecosystem services. Finally, the governance discussion also produced key questions related to **managing conflicting demands placed on UF-NBS**.

The knowledge and indicators discussion also highlighted key questions related to several themes. Participants raised questions about the **challenges in quantifying the social and political processes related to UF-NBS**. Many proposals were also raised relating to environmental science, particularly **measurements of ecosystem health and its interaction with human health**. A final group of key questions related to identifying the most appropriate **indicators for comparing how UF-NBS are implemented** across diverse international contexts in both the EU and China.

In the business and management discussion, many of the questions emphasized the **challenge of economically quantifying the value of UF-NBS** and of placing a monetary value on intangible natural processes. Other key questions focused on identifying ways to ensure a stable stream of financing to implement UF-NBS. Additionally, participants proposed numerous questions related to the management of UF-NBS.

The multifunctionalities and dilemmas group raised key questions related to numerous themes. Some questions were broadly related to the **challenge of confronting multifunctional demands** placed on UF-NBS. Many other questions related to the potentially **conflicting pressures for urban spatial and economic growth**, and the **preservation of land for UF-NBS**. Moreover, **climate change and biodiversity** were also frequently mentioned as major challenges for further exploration.

Table 1: Key Questions

Governance	Knowledge & Indicators	Business & Management Models	Multifunctionalities and dilemmas
<p>Governance Models: scale & participation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevant governance models: who participates or not? (Gov. institutions, private sector, civil society, citizens...) • How to influence and create reasonable needs and expectations of various groups of stakeholders (citizens, local government, private sector...) • Co-governance - bottom up engagement in developing UF-NBS and sharing of power between fund holders and local residents/communities - training packages and guidelines (use local languages and avoid overly technical 'professional' discussion. • How to better cooperate between the different public administrations and stakeholders? • how to coordinate cooperation between various public institutions on various levels? • How to enable institutional collaboration, connectivity, and networks at various levels? • How to better cooperate between the different public administrations and stakeholders? • How to include NBS in planning and policy frameworks at metropolitan level? • What scale do we manage UF at? - In both EU and China, it is typically at the city and neighborhood level • In Chinese case city clusters are also key <p>Land management</p>	<p>Social Sciences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to assess the impact of (UF-NBS) co-creation processes? • cultural and social data • How to show the association of biodiversity in urban areas to the health <p>Policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to best manage such knowledge, and translate knowledge into policy-action? • Assessment and measurement of continuity, various types of continuity • How to develop and mobilize applied knowledge and know-how (socio/political knowledge vs. natural science) ? <p>Environmental Science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify most-suitable links indicator with respect to data + NBS action • Water & soil permeability: an interesting research question concerns water, where it goes, and how • UF and public health related quality assurance • Realise maps of ecosystems and ecosystem services that integrate and transcend administrative boundaries? • Biodiversity data • How to realise useful and relevant inventories of trees? (or are tree inventories really useful?) • human health 	<p>Quantifying UF-NBS value</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the value of nature, the preservation of biological diversity, sustainability, more careful resource management, improved acceptance of environmental and resource policy...? • How to "monetize" the UF vs housing issues? • Can we rate ecosystem services with money? How? • What for? • The best nature-based solutions for each case and situation, and their cost and benefits? • What is the relation between monetary costs and benefits of UF-NBS measures? how to measure them in a meaningful and useful manner • How to communicate economic benefits? → how to visualise and encourage? → maps, GIS visualisations presentations • How can NBS/ES be integrated into the cities accounting? • We need data! data of the impact, of the costs.... • how to quantify the ES and convert to money? 	<p>Urban growth</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rapid urbanization in Chinese cities dilemmas • Green cities vs. compact cities dilemmas • What is the future of different urban tree species in fast growing cities and under warmer and drier climatic conditions? • UF-NBS in mobility infrastructure (e.g., streets) - more space for trees, less for cars • Potential and threat related to the mobility infrastructure • limited land for ecological construction • UF-NBS in private land • Research on empty housing and price differences between building restoration vs. construction • Environmental quality vs. social inclusion dilemmas (eco-gentrification, green-washing...) <p>Climate change and biodiversity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The impacts of climate change and biodiversity loss/often contradictory in cities • biodiversity versus public use • What are the requirements of a climate-adaptive reforestation in terms of management and

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • how to protect the natural forest land? • The concept of urban managers and residents' pursuit of regional traditional culture affect the management of urban forests • long term governance models, need to think in terms of managing and taking care of the trees and forests • How to determine the total amount and reasonable spatial distribution of urban forest for different types of cities (plains or mountainous areas) and different sizes? • Local level can include rivers + wetland resources <p>Pedagogy/education/awareness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • what role can education/ learning formats play? • How to build the public awareness on the value of green areas and ecosystem services? • Key actors: resident needs • Residents also have a heavy need for ecological recreational places provided by urban forests • Importance of interface between policy making - spatial (space and time) planning - training and guidance (i.e., guidelines needed in local languages) in needed. • How to influence the decision maker • How to cooperate better with the policy makers so that they would listen and not just to hear <p>Conflict Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • importance of different paradigms/ways of thinking about urban forests and their management, and resulting "clashes" between actors and how to resolve it 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the optimal amount of tree (urban forest) cover for projects to aim for to maximise ecosystem services in different contexts, and is this different if the urban forest is considered from a nature-based solution position as opposed to biophysical green infrastructure? • How to assess the impacts of climate change on UF-NBS and their benefits? • ecosystem health of urban forest <p>International Comparison</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effectiveness of UF-NBS and how do we best measure it for a comparative study between Europe and China? • Can the China Forest City KPIs be treated into EU - English translation needed • What are the best indicators? • How to assess knowledge and better share information on NBS and related initiatives • how to compare the data from different cities in China and Europe • Which "process indicators" should be used to compare the different co-design processes? 	<p>Stable finance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to adapt financing and budgets for long-term UF-NBS to electoral cycles • How to guarantee a continuous funding and a continuity of green policies so that they can be effective, and failure can be accounted for (as trees are living systems)? • dealing with public good and private goods, depending on the situation • How to deal with scarcity & temporal mismatch of financial resources? • Investment case - Important for EU, national government, and business more than municipalities? open question - presentational evidence case needed with graphical outputs <p>Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to optimise maintenance costs of river parks exploitation? how to create maintenance standards? • importance of operational expenditure • new ways to integrate nature in planning instruments • Is case a challenge? • How to systematize a business model? Can there be a typology of BMs? 	<p>costs, policy and planning options, and monitoring?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changing climate with hotter days and dehydrated soils=> how can tree-based solutions be implemented sustainably so that their advantages can be used and experienced by everyone? <p>Multifunctionality</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • definition of different types of multifunctional ES-combinations and related management strategies. • How to include multifunctionality better already in green strategies? Now climate and biodiversity are often key targets • How multifunctionality and co-benefits of UF-NBS are a) achieved and b) promoted? • Health impacts of different green area types • Food provision as a key ecosystem service
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • how to align different demands for ecosystem services from urban forest with the "supply"? Sub questions/approaches: participatory mapping of ecosystem services demands. Contrasting it with natural science data on the provision. Understanding the effect and shortcomings of current governance arrangements. Suggest changes 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the issues are about power sharing between fund holders and communities in UF-NBS co-design and the tools to support this. Also invent case tools - graphical punchy outputs but not just € also quality of life etc. 	
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Step 2 : Prioritize research questions

The second portion of the breakout session invited participants to narrow down the scope of questions proposed in part 1 and select only a few key priorities for each of the four themes that should be the focus of research in T2.2 going forward. The Mural results of this discussion are presented in *Table 2* below :

- The governance group chose to focus on several key themes: coordination (across actors and scales), inclusion of stakeholders, and public awareness.
- The knowledge and indicators group chose to emphasize topics related to quantifying ecosystem services and cultural knowledge of UF-NBS, as well as the importance of comparative indicators for China and the EU.
- The business and management models discussion selected the monetization of ecosystem services and developing UF-NBS accounting/ budgeting metrics as the key research priorities in this theme.
- The multifunctionalities discussion chose to emphasize issues related to both multifunctional benefits of UF-NBS, as well as potential trade-offs.

Table 2: Research Priorities

Governance	Knowledge & Indicators	Business & Management Models	Multifunctionalities and dilemmas
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scale of governance, mode of governance, and land distribution • 1) perceptions of different societal groups and awareness and how to measure systematically, 2) Different paradigms/interests of players and how to integrate them (coordination!), 3) inclusive governance approaches 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realize maps of ecosystems and ecosystem services that integrate and transcend administrative boundaries? • How to collect data on green areas uses in a cost-effective way. Monitoring needed • on INDICATORS: compare data China/Europe, methods to advance citizen engagement in "monitoring", citizen monitoring, also how to include the "cultural/emotional" importance of UF-NBS. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can we rate ecosystem services with money? How? • How to systematize a business model? Can there be a typology of BMs? • The best nature- based solutions for each case 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trade-offs between the benefits (health of ppl vs. other benefits) • what is the role of multifunctionality for benefits of NBS (e.g. health impacts of different green area types) and what are trade-offs • How to include multifunctionality better already

<p>(participation) and their "performance";</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to build the public awareness and communication on the value of green areas and ecosystem services? • How to convince the public • Expectation from public vs. government planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to compare data btw Eur and China because different units • Effectiveness of UF-NBS and how do we best measure it for a comparative study between Europe and China? • UF and public health related quality assurance • How to best manage such knowledge, and translate knowledge into policy-action? • For Biodiversity the are a lot well-known indicators for comparison of several data (locality independent) • For some ecosystem services (e.g., CO₂ sequestration) universal and comparable indicators [large CO₂ sequestration by trees = large mitigation of negative UHI effects] • ratio between investment and return in terms of ecological service 	<p>and situation, and their cost and benefits?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can NBS/ES be integrated into the cities accounting? 	<p>in green strategies? Now climate and biodiversity are often key targets</p>
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Step 3: Investigative approaches to conduct research

In the third section of Part 1 of the workshops, participants were invited to propose ways to conduct research through the rest of the CLEARING HOUSE project, in order to respond to the key questions identified in previous sections. The Mural results from this section are provided in *Table 3* below.

Most approaches were listed by the group discussing UF-NBS governance, and they can be considered to fall into several categories which largely encapsulate the proposals across all group discussions. Several participants emphasized the importance of visiting the sites where UF-NBS are being implemented and **conducting field work**. Attendees also drew attention to the **field laboratories in T4.4** which could potentially be expanded to suite the research needs of T2.2. **Surveys of the public** were also listed as a potential method for investigating public awareness of UF-NBS. Participants also cited **targeted stakeholder workshops** as another potentially fruitful method for conducting research. Another approach that was mentioned by several participants was **studying the planning work related to UF-NBS**, which could also include potential GIS studies. Several responses also mentioned participatory data gathering, including citizen science. Finally, **traditional research methods** such as interviews with experts or practitioners, as well as desk research were also proposed.

Table 3: Investigative Approach

Governance	Knowledge & Indicators	Business & Management Models	Multifunctionalities and dilemmas
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<p>Site visits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • visiting a site different times over a long period • Develop something in the field and then get feedback (Importance of implementation to onboard stakeholders) • In person visits and exchange will be key - iterative research with several meetings between CS leaders and scientists across EU and China • Field investigation <p>Surveys</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • questionnaire with public • surveys • Questionnaire survey of residents' wishes <p>Workshops</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops with clear objectives/mandate • analysis of key preferences of key players, then in workshop discussion about how to deal with them and find consent ways, also reflecting ES demands from society <p>Field laboratories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • field laboratories be expanded into a co-learning platform on governance as well as technical interventions <p>Planning studies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of how the citizen values are taken into consideration in actual implementation of environment planning • analyzing current ways of planning, understand how it can be made more inclusive (relating it to education) • Our project team may work together on a specific urban forest planning and construction project <p>Participatory data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • participatory mapping to understand key demands towards UF-NBS from DIFFERENT societal groups • citizen science <p>Interviews</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss with government department • Face-to-face interview 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It could be great to ask citizen groups to develop bottom up a set of "indicators" they would like to see monitored, and then involve them thereafter in monitoring • Our project team can jointly research and propose an urban forest evaluation index • Measurement methodology • Field investigation • questionnaire with public • Discuss with stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • co-design workshops with business • Clarify what role of the project next to the case studies • Select several typical urban forest business operation mode investigation • Field investigation • based on the current collected data, potential data and open data • Synthesize on basis of case studies and technological documents • cluster the questions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GIS approach and interviews / observations
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<p>Other</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To collect relevant documents • comparative analyses 			
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Step 4 : Expected outputs from the research in T2.2

The breakout discussions of Part 1 of the workshop concluded by inviting all participants to reflect on what the expected outputs from the research in T2.2 should be. The results from group discussions are available below in *Table 4*.

A consistent theme across the groups was that the research should be **closely tied to tangible practice in co-designing and implementing UF-NBS**. Participants proposed numerous outputs that could serve to offer best practices from previous experience implementing UF-NBS and also offer useful guidance for current practitioners.

Table 4: Expected Outputs

Governance	Knowledge & Indicators	Business & Management Models	Multifunctionalities and dilemmas
<p>Best Practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Successful experiences (Planning, co-design, managing, ...) that could be replicated • UN handbook on NBS offers key indicators • Best practices on UF-NBS • Innovative methods of how to do participatory research with feasible efforts <p>Guidance for Practitioners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • how to balance biodiversity and public use • Let the city planning be implemented, and the needs of the residents can be realized. • Differences between governors' and citizens' expectations • Governance instruction • Lifelong learning • Put forward the municipal forest construction guidelines for the city-related case cities • We will be exploring further the question on what type of guidance decision makers will need 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban Forest Construction Index System • Standard or regulation • Demonstration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management models • Technical manuals • Types of business models for Sino-EU cities 	

3 Results from Workshop Part 2

Step 1 : Business Models and Investment Cases

The collaborative portion of Part 2 of the workshop began with a discussion section to feed into T4.1, which focuses on designing business models and investment case studies for UF-NBS. The Mural results of this discussion are presented in *Table 5* below.

Participants listed several **costs they incur to implement UF-NBS**. In particular procuring trees emerged as a major capital expenditure, while maintenance appeared to be a major operational expense.

When asked to list **major issues to financing UF-NBS**, participants emphasized the competition of numerous grey infrastructure projects for public funding, as well as the need to prove the cost effectiveness of UF-NBS and attract private investment alongside public funding. With respect to available finance mechanisms, many participants cited public funding mechanisms, with a lesser emphasis on private and non-profit options as well.

Participants then were asked to focus **on why private actors would implement UF-NBS**. Responses typically emphasized the economic benefits that UF-NBS can provide, as well as the impact such efforts could have on corporate social responsibility, and because public policy may oblige such measures.

Then participants elaborated on the **role of NGO’s in supporting UF-NBS**. Their responses indicated NGO’s have a major role to play in raising public awareness about the benefits of UF-NBS, as well as in capacity building for stakeholders, and allowing for knowledge exchange between different cities around the world.

Finally, participants listed a wide range of **costs if UF-NBS are not implemented**, including dangers to human and environmental health.

Table 5: Task T4.1 - Urban Forests as Nature-Based Solutions (UF-NBS) Business Models and Investment Cases

List costs you incur in the implementation and operational phases (capital expenditure and operational costs)	List issues to finance capital expenditure and operational costs	How do you finance capital expenditures and operational costs?	What motivates a CEO to make a decision to implement UF-NBS?	What is the role of NGOs in promoting a UF-NBS culture?	What Most of inaction you think UF-NBS should address at a state level?
Capital expenditure - implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> design and planning (bigger, more diverse team, lack of experience) 	Competing projects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> explaining and convincing the public that green infrastructure is 	Public <ul style="list-style-type: none"> via markets (public markets) Green bonds compensation model of scenery 	Economics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can generate a certain profit in the short term, and have a positive impact on the future market Saved sickness leave costs 	Public Awareness <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting knowledge and awareness of UF-NBS impacts at the local level as well as citizen engagement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> pollution/ health inactive population (leading to welfare diseases)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Procurement of trees • Investments are more time-consuming and unpredictable(as all innovations) • Manpower(planting the trees) • How to improve the ability of urban forestry to cope with climate change • water <p>Operational costs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • maintenance costs are the hardest to follow • Land transfer costs (Forest vs. agriculture) • NBS are cheaper to maintain than conventional ones (no issue :) <p>Externalization of costs is the issue!</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More than 5 million funds have been raised, with about 2 million funds in place. It is mainly used for the purchase of monitoring equipment, and other expenditures include labor costs and material costs. 	<p>more cost effective than grey</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budget is devoted to other projects that are not UF-NbS related. • UF-management is not "sexy"- it does not reach the headlines in newspapers <p>Cost</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operational costs • Continuous maintenance costs can be an issue. • NBS ARE CHEAPER, that is proven. <p>Private vs Public</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target groups, e.g., private companies or state-owned companies • Public acceptance and support for the selected solutions • Private contractors can be cheaper than public sector direct workforce but difficult to build a long term relationship especially due to tendering rules 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect additional taxes on polluting companies • Main Municipal Budget (part of the budget is a Citizen Budget for projects selected by voting) + EU funds and other than Main City Budget • EU funds • Transfer of financial resources from other municipal tasks • Ecological compensation model • city budget • Strive for government and ecological-related special funds, technical service fees, etc., for the implementation of this project • developing projects in some countries <p>Private</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private Public Partnership Projects • support for the acceptance by employees • Operational costs • Marketing ES (CO₂ storage) • Cooperate with enterprises, invite bids or 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other conveniences (land or business authorization) that can be obtained by investing in other projects after participating in this project <p>Policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local law and obligation (spatial planning, etc.) • Obligation of water retention within the property • reduction of taxes, or some other benefits from state • Sharing of government objectives in the local agenda. <p>Corporate Social Responsibility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusion in shareholders report as evidence of social responsibility • If it has the support of the board of Directors • Peer group pressure from other CEOs of other companies especially competitors • Greening the company; CO₂ offsetting • Avoid the impact and attention of campaign groups e.g., Greenpeace • Climate change adaptation & ensuring ES supply 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • often they are the main voice of all residents (depends on the case) • creating societal "trends" <p>Skills & Knowledge</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Think-Tank (know-how, good practice, networking) • can have leading role in establishing NBS • Stewardship role in UF-NBS management • Plan and implement urban ecosystem issues that the government has not paid attention to. <p>Networking</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • building the bridge between UF, UF management, society, economical partner • Through their membership (many have millions of members) - education role and also members become influential in the political process. • help to overcome silos, initiate the dialogue between stakeholders 	<p>such as obesity etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sensitivity to climate change and other municipal challenges (eco, socio, etc.) • Mental health issues and also many health issues • growing impact of heat waves • Public opinions are sometimes ignored. • Taking the improvement of the urban environment as an important assessment indicator for urban development • decreasing amount of water in cities, drought • Regular monitoring and evaluation and inclusion of evaluation results in urban
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> volunteering / community engagement in maintenance (instead of finances directly) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Why are private partners financing NBS? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - if they earn money, - if they become famous, - if the media inform people: this is a good firm, buy goods. 	<p style="color: red;">select some companies related to the project to enhance the sociality of the project</p> <p>Non-profit</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> charity / donations etc. Grants from NGOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> personal motivation; family and health of the family PR goals CSR policy <li style="color: red;">Can promote the positive image of the company highlighting benefits to employees Reputation of the company 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> development assessment unliveable city!!! environmental issues of various types (depending on location etc) Cheaper and more long lasting than a grey alternative
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Step 2 : UF-NBS Tools Development

Participants were then asked to provide their input for Task 4.2. This task will focus on the development and testing of distinct decision support tools for facilitating the deployment of UF-NBS. Specifically, two tools will be developed during this task. The first is an (online) **application for developing, modelling, and assessing UF-NBS scenarios** in urban development with the aim to optimize UF-NBS for cost-effective and performant service delivery at diverging scales. The second tool will be a simple but effective **global benchmarking tool to compare UF-NBS** in different settings. Workshop participants were asked to consider the objectives, functionality, and integration of both tools.

With respect to the UF-NBS scenario tool, many participants expressed a desire for comparative data related to UF-NBS in their city and sought a functional, graphical representation of proposed models. Moreover, for the global benchmarking tool, participants expressed a desire for qualitative and quantitative assessments of UF-NBS performance that could allow decision makers to have comparative insights about results between cities. The full range of participant responses can be seen in *Table 6* below.

Table 6: Task T4.2 - Urban Forests as Nature-Based Solutions Tools Development

Specific Tool	Objectives: What are knowledge gaps of users (e.g., regarding certain challenges in your city) which can be filled by each tool?	Functionality: What should the tool be able to deliver in terms of handling, functionality, or expected output?	Integration: How should the results look like in order to ensure a realistic uptake by key users and stakeholders and adoption into urban planning practice?
UF-NBS Scenario Tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> using models to compare past present and future scientific foundation on how concrete NBS are addressing concrete challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> scenarios should be clearly defined (what is a scenario, how can scenarios be described); Good 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Graphics that are simple to understand the advantages of UF-NBS Graphical format with nice design

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lack of simple, numerical, and visual explanation of how the city with forests (trees) differs from the one without + the consequences • timescale (how long NBS lasts, but also how long does it take that they fulfil their potential) • the real contribution for specific ES (e.g., mitigate the heat waves, improve the air quality) • Role models - examples of good practices • establishing links between scenarios and the "world of the target groups" • Clear & advanced indicators on NBS • awareness of what NBS are - that is more general but important • The relationship between urban grey buildings and green Spaces • Knowledge gap on what are the actual value in money of all the ecosystem services that nature provides in cities • comparisons of challenges (e.g., floods, storms potential in future) and how NBS can contribute • Lack of knowledge on the hi-tech instruments available for mapping urban land surfaces 	<p>examples how to describe scenarios</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address local spatial planning priorities - relevant to issues that may not occur elsewhere - perhaps suggest a menu approach • modelling • Mapping for different scenarios • The simulation evaluates the ecosystem services of urban forests • Outcomes (figure or table or graphic pic) should be clear and easy to understand, especially for the group without professional background • stakeholders mapping • Describe the possible changes in the future • Cost effectiveness of different scenarios including no action • Guide innovative city planning • To what extent is it possible to make the tools universal? Taking into account varied conditions in different cities • The output mode (chart, or diagram) of the results, so that people without professional background can understand • Functionality-simple and easy to use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follow KISS principle Keep it simple • Designed for decision makers rather than technocrats (these generally have no power) • Clear principles; may be even some "minimal standards" of good practice • Don't forget paper - many decision makers are NOT digital natives. • graphic tool: easy to use and respond to multiple users demands • the language should be very easy understandable; links to studies and further going reports could be given. • versions understandable for average citizens should be available • locally specific - as much as possible (at least on level of our cases) • Clear usable app used via all mobile phones • Graphical, attractive 'facade' + access to technical knowledge/details • (for interested ones, professionals) • case studies with "proof" of results • Simple visualisations, convincing numbers • Entrance point to CH results (guidelines, reports, CS, etc.)
<p>Global Benchmarking Tool</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • criteria/indicators of NBS contributions • How do you take into account the differences between cities? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlighting strengths and weaknesses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage twinning and leader - follower cities

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comprehensive view vs. details • how to create the tools for multiple needs (the demands vary cities) • 10 key indicators of sustainable NBS • Platform of platforms: platform linking all existing platforms with monitoring, research programs etc • How 'realistic' is 'global' and actually is it desirable as most NBS are local in nature and impact. Also, relationship with IUCN guidelines • How to know what is a strong NbS for UF-NBS specifically (IUCN Global Standard for NbS) • Soft facts as well as hard facts i.e., wellness, wellbeing index etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The possibility to identify the gaps/flaws in 'our' city and to direct users to material on how to fix the situation • Whether or not you get monetized data that makes it easier for people to evaluate • Suggestions/recommendations for tools and action to bring in line with the global framework • Quantify the impact of UF-NBS on the environment, economy, society, and ecology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive competition, comparison of different aspects/general situation • comparing similar cities and UF-NBS solutions around the globe • Entrance point to CH results (guidelines, reports, CS, etc.) • All aspects are classified and compared • assessment of qualitative and quantitative indicators in some simple way • Users can continue to offer feedback to continuously optimizing tools • Data driven but easily transferable into communications for a more general public
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Step 3 : Suggestions for T4.3

The following exercise invited participants to offer their insights for Task 4.3. This task will draw upon the findings of WP1-3 to develop thematic guidelines related to UF-NBS delivery. These guidelines will serve to assist local authorities, consultants, decision makers, civil society and other stakeholders in Europe, China and worldwide in delivering UF-NBS to their communities and local stakeholders. The task will focus on creating four sets of guidelines which will be produced focused on the following critical areas:

1. cost-effective urban ecosystem restoration, ecological rehabilitation and new planning approaches and methods;
2. mechanisms for public and stakeholder engagement in planning and managing UF-NBS, with specific attention towards less-privileged groups (see T5.2 for definition of “less-privileged groups”);
3. management guidelines for UF-NBS, which will deal with planning, policy and delivery;
4. change management and institutional reform for the better management of UF-NBS.

For each of these four thematic guidelines, participants were invited to offer content suggestions and to volunteer to take part in developing a specific guideline. The results of their inputs can be seen below in *Table 7*.

Table 7: Task T4.3 - Thematic Guidelines

1. Cost effective urban ecosystem restoration, ecological rehabilitation and new planning approaches and methods.	2. Mechanisms for public and stakeholder engagement in planning & managing UF-NBS with specific attention towards less privileged groups	3. Management guidelines for UF-NBS, which will deal with planning policy and delivery	4. Change management and institutional reform for the better management of UF-NBS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reclamation of former industrial land i.e., ex-coalfield community NBS management organisations ("from community urban forestry to community NBSolutionary") Comparing costs with benefits Balance of supply and demand of ecosystem services Emphasis on areas/topics where NBS have no real alternatives This guideline should probably build on T4.1 examples of CBA of UF-NBS for restoration miniCS from cities (esp. CS cities) Tailor measures to local conditions and target the core needs of different cities urban planning principles for NBS <p>Benefits from well- functioning NBS network (added value in comparison to ind. NBS)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create NBS community circles (community NBSolutionaries) socially innovative initiatives (support bottom-up engagement) Well-designed and realized public participatory processes on NBS (mechanisms + CS) events in NBS Justice for urban and rural residents to enjoy ecological services creation of awards /certificates Balance between different departments (construction vs protection) public awareness building outdoor events how to incorporate different forms of knowledge How to gain momentum and political power (different models of activities/ movements) different participation methods (e.g., consultation of citizens by random) examples of mechanisms of co-governance of UF-NBS including limits and potential pay attention to the groups with mental distress or physical inconvenience and provide them with the freedom to publish their appeals anonymously under the protection of privacy. Environmental & Social Management System (ESMS) could be done during the procedure miniCS from cities (esp. CS cities) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Considerations on how to deal with existing dilemmas (e.g., tree planting vs parking...) Model plans and strategies than can be easily adapted NBS Policy Briefs Handbooks and other tools such as APPS that can be used 'on-site' Regulations that support UF NBS How to facilitate tree preservation on private land Standard tender documents that can be adapted "Architecture" kind of guidelines on how to develop land without breaking ecological connectivity <p>miniCS from cities (esp. CS cities)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reform of delivery departments away from trad arboriculture towards ecosystem maximisation. Creative ideas on how to promote horizontal and vertical cooperation among government offices From Silo to Synthesis: new forms of institutional interactions Needed policy changes - what is missing New agencies created such as partnership projects such as Community Forests in England. Specific ways to improve management Clearer and more specific institutional division of responsibilities inclusion of society from early stages Cross departmental UF-NBS coordinators to encourage joined up municipal working Educational programmes from early ages Task force approach Cross-sectoral collaboration (umbrella organisation) miniCS from cities (esp. CS cities)

D3.3 Sino European Codesign Report V0

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Differences in different countries, the universality of the guidelines • "demonstration" solutions to build public awareness and support strongly link UF-NBS to public health, both mental and physical, provide proofs of this link 		
Team Members			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jiali-CAF-RIF • Dennis • Tomasz Bergier (TSF) • Jiajia Zhao • Clive (coordinator) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ivana Zivojinovic (BOKU) • Karolina Maliszewska. Agnieszka Czachowska (TSF) • Clive (coordinator) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tomasz Bergier (TSF) • Ivana Zivojinovic (BOKU) • Nic (VUB) • Clive (coordinator) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ivana Zivojinovic (BOKU) • Dennis • Ving Wu • Clive (coordinator)

Step 4 : Field laboratories

The workshop then turned its focus to Task 4.4. This task will design and test promising UF-NBS in real-world situations in selected case studies. The field laboratories will serve as a space where the tools developed in T4.1 and T4.2 will be piloted. During this section of the workshop, participants were first invited to reflect on the meaning of UF-NBS laboratories for them. Then they were invited to consider specific areas of interest they would like to test in the field laboratories. Next, participants offered criteria that should be considered when choosing a partner city to implement the field laboratories. Finally, participants were invited to list cities in both Europe and China that could be interested in implementing the field laboratories. The responses related to T4.4 can be seen in *Table 8* below.

Table 8: Task T4.4- Field Laboratories

1- UF-NBS field laboratory meaning	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • urban-rural comparison • long-term positioning monitoring • explore new approaches • replicating CH interventions • give the feedbacks which can help to improve or adjust the tools • field verification of the operability of theoretical knowledge and improvement • introducing some new approach in existing NBS/city • learn about multiple functions of trees through games and trainings 	
2- Areas of interest you would like to be tested?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CH education package • public reaction? • scenario model/ Scenario tool • Scenario simulation tool • Comparison between UF-NBS and non UF-NBS approach - modelling exercise. • Business models and mechanisms (2x) • Benchmark tool (ideally in all CH CS cities) • Investments cases • Residential area (2x) • Governance models 	
3- Criteria to select case studies to test the tool	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Willing to volunteer! • Areas with faster urbanization • Areas of ES • Ideally at least one in EU and one in China • Some involvement in civil society • The places where people can have outdoor activities. • If the city is highly motivated • Where there is local funding • Strong commitment of local partners • Where it's an already ongoing process • willingness of private entities to engage • declaration to implement the outcomes 	
4- Specify the name of your city interested in testing the tool	
European Cities	Chinese Cities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kraków, PL • Ghent (BE)? • Barcelona 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 北京- Beijing • 宁波- Ningbo city (Forest city cluster planning) • 杭州- Hangzhou

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paris • Fontainebleau • Bonn (Kottenforst) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 厦门- Xiamen • -广州 Guangzhou • 大湾区城市群 Greater Bay Area City Group • 深圳 Shenzhen
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Step 5 : webinar platform for knowledge exchange and upskilling

The following exercise was a shorter request for contribution from workshop participants, relating to Task 5.3. This task provides a knowledge exchange and learning platform to provide online upskilling training and development support for users of CLEARING HOUSE products. Participants were invited to list any topic they would like for a webinar to consider (relating to T4.3), and to list potential speakers that could be invited to present. Their contributions are listed in *Table 9* below.

Table 9: Task 5.3 Maintaining a webinar platform for knowledge exchange and upskilling

Add here any content that you would like to see covered in the CLEARING HOUSE webinar series - the themes are prescribed and linked directly to task 4.3 (see titles above) but the content is not fixed	Speakers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • guidelines for cost-effective UF-NBS planning • business model case studies and how to learn from EU and China • (inspiring) examples of concrete projects/results • how to integrate in practice the IUCN global standard criteria in UF-NBS • Governance aspects for UF-NBS upscale and importance of ... • (Un)successful UF-NBS projects in China and Europe 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tomasz! • IUCN • The webinar on public engagement talks about less privileged groups could one of the speakers come from such a background? • Romena Huq (Scotland)

Step 6 : workshop conclusion / innovation roadmap

During the Sino European co-design event, LGI shared with partners the innovation roadmap of CLEARING HOUSE (see figure below). LGI walked partners through the innovation steps, in particular the tools development as part of task T4.2 and the sustainable business model innovations and investment cases tailored for UF-NBS (T4.1). The workshop organised was also an opportunity to understand the expectations from the audience for the WP4 specifically. All the results developed in WP4 and WP2 (second phase, T2.2) will be detailed in the exploitation plan that will aim to sustain CLEARING HOUSE results after the end of the project.

Figure 5: Task T5.5 Innovation Roadmap

CONCLUSION

The Sino-EU co-design workshop provided a fruitful opportunity for European and Chinese stakeholders to engage in constructive dialogue about a wide range of topics related to UF-NBS. The results of these discussions will now feed into multiple tasks across the CLEARING HOUSE project. The comparative case study analysis in T2.2 and the actions and tools developed in WP4 and WP5 will inform their actions based on these results.

As next steps in Task 3.1, local case study coordinators will organize two further series of local co-learning stakeholder workshops. These workshops will introduce the existing research work on UF-NBS discussed during this co-design workshop, while also providing a more context-specific analysis. Local case study coordinators will then report and discuss their findings with local stakeholders and citizens. These discussions will be shared through the consortium.

Effectively implementing UF-NBS requires a diverse range of knowledge, spanning across biological, environmental, social, economic, and political sciences. Engaging in trans-disciplinary dialogues such as those offered by the Sino-EU co-design workshop is thus vital to ensure that decision makers are exposed to perspectives and lessons from across the world. Ideally this workshop represents another step in a longer-term dialogue about how urban forests can promote social and environmental sustainability in both Europe and China.

ANNEX

Full scale images of the final murals produced during the codesign workshop are presented on the following pages.

INTRODUCTION

1 Game Rules 活动概要

- This is a safe and respectful environment.
- Everyone is strongly encouraged to participate!
- Translators will facilitate the exchanges, speaking slowly may help!
- Beyond all, this is the occasion to have fun, interact and get to know each other better!

2 TIPS TO USE MURAL MURAL 使用说明

- Click on the panel button on the left to start drawing.
- Double click to create post-it notes.
- You can change its color & size.
- You can write in the post-it notes by clicking on it starting to write.
- You can zoom in by using your mouse.
- You can draw or add images using the panel on the left.
- You can crop/erase an existing post-it, and click to change its content.
- You can hide or show your cursor by hovering over your post-it at the bottom of the screen.
- If you are lost on the mural, you can click on the facilitator's icon to go back to the current step of the workshop.
- Click on the panel button on the left to start drawing. You can see CTRL-Z to go back and CTRL-E to go on.

3 AGENDA 议程

- Key research questions 0 25 min
- Research priorities 0 5 min
- Investigative approach & Expected outputs 0 10 min

Workshop duration

0 45min

4 SPLIT TO GROUPS 分组讨论

- GROUP 1: EU and Chinese partners with official translation. **Manorport**. Facilitator: Dagmar Heese, Co-facilitator: Sam Whitmore, Chinese translation: Pina Mischen. All topics.
- GROUP 2: EU-Chinese partners with informal translation. **Break-out room 2**. **Governance + Knowledge**. Facilitator: Nicolas de Felice, Co-facilitator: Leticia Diaz, Chinese support: Tiyun Sun.
- GROUP 3: EU-Chinese partners with informal translation. **Break-out room 2**. **Business / Mgt Models + Multifunctionality**. Facilitator: Jialin, Co-facilitator: Joanne Scherze, Chinese support: Weizang Pu.

IDEA PARKING LOT

Feeling inspired but it's not directly related to the exercise? please park it here

Color Key

Collective Research Design - GROUP 1 研究设计 - 小组一

1 核心问题

梳理研究方向, 明确核心问题, 明确在哪些类型的POI区域进行重点数据收集POI?

1 Key Questions

- Divide on the questions, generate sub-questions, clarify research direction.
- Complete empty post-its or add content to existing post-its by clicking on writer panel to lead to it.
- 0 25 min

2 优先排序

对整理好的研究问题进行优先级排序, 包括哪些有挑战以及最难的案例城市?

2 Research Priorities

- Prioritize research areas, both for the whole consortium and for individual cities.
- 0 5 min

3 调查方法

明确研究主题, 明确具体方法逻辑, 明确哪些是具体的调查途径, 调查方法?

3 Investigative Approach

- Identify concrete approaches to investigate these topics? how to do the research. Ex. are direct experimentation or relations (questionnaires, focus tests, research by experts, ...), media observation (ethnographic observation, interviews, focus groups, ...)
- 0 5 min

4 预期成果

对整理好的研究问题进行头脑风暴

4 Expected Outputs

- Brainstorm about research outputs.
- 0 5 min

Agenda	议程
9:00-9:10: Introduction	15:00- 15:10: 介绍
9:10-9:25: Overview of CLEARING HOUSE Project	15:10-15:25: CLEARING HOUSE项目总体介绍
9:25-10:00: Three topics presented by Chinese stakeholders	15:25-16:00: 中方参会人员主题发言
10:00-10:10: Break	16:00 - 16:10: 茶歇
10:10-10:40: Business Model & Investment cases workshop	16:40 - 17:05: UF-NBS工具开发讨论
10:40-11:05: Urban Forests as Nature-Based Solutions Tools development workshop	17:05 - 17:30: 主题导则讨论
11:05-11:30: Thematic guidelines workshop	17:30 - 17:45: 针对测试场地、网络平台以及知识与创新的讨论
11:30-11:45: Laboratory fields workshop, Webinar platform for knowledge and Innovation roadmap presentations	17:45-18:00: 回到Zoom会议室, 中方做最后一个主题发言
11:45-12:00: Move back to Zoom for topic presentations by Chinese stakeholder and wrap-up	

How to use Mural?	如何使用MURAL?
★ Double click to create post-it notes	★ 双击鼠标可创建便利贴
★ You can change its colour & size.	★ 您可以修改便利贴的颜色和大小
★ You can write in the post-it note by clicking on it starting to write.	★ 您可以通过点击便利贴后进行编辑
★ You can zoom in by using your mouse.	★ 您可以用鼠标放大和缩小页面
★ You can draw or add images using the panel on the left.	★ 您可以通过左边的菜单栏进行画图或添加图片
★ You can hide or show your cursor by hovering over your initials at the bottom of the screen.	★ 您可以通过悬停在屏幕底部的姓名框来隐藏或显示你的光标
★ You can select multiple items by selecting ctrl+shift at the same time	★ 您可以通过ctrl+shift键进行多项选择

欢迎
WELCOME

Parking Lot
Please let us your suggestions / feedbacks here

Task T4.1 - Urban Forests as Nature-Based Solutions (UF-NBS) Business models and Investment cases (25 min) 商业模式 (25分钟)					
List costs you incur in the implementation and operational costs	List issues to finance capital expenditures and operational costs	How do you finance capital expenditures and operational costs?	What motivates a CEO to make a decision to implement UF-NBS?	What is the role of NGOs in promoting a UF-NBS culture?	What cost of inaction you think UF-NBS should address at a state level?
请列出您在执行UF-NBS过程的成本 (业务和支出费用)	请列出UF-NBS资本支出融资的相关问题	请问您是如何为UF-NBS资本支出融资?	什么能够促使 (某公司) 的总经理来实施UF-NBS?	非盈利组织在推进UF-NBS中具有怎样的作用或角色?	您认为UF-NBS应该在国家层面上解决哪些不作为的问题?

Task T4.3 - Thematic guidelines (25 min) 主题导则 (25分钟)				
<p>Could the guidelines be value guidelines and not just a tool?</p>	<p>1. Cost effective urban ecosystem restoration, ecological rehabilitation and new planning approaches and methods.</p> <p>1. 具有成本效益的城市生态系统恢复、生态恢复和新的规划方式及方法</p>	<p>2. Mechanisms for public and stakeholder engagement in planning & managing UF-NBS with specific attention towards less privileged groups</p> <p>2. 公众和利益相关者参与规划和管理UF-NBS的机制, 特别关注弱势群体</p>	<p>3. Management guidelines for UF-NBS, which will deal with planning policy and delivery</p> <p>3. UF-NBS的管理准则, 它将处理规划政策和交付问题</p>	<p>4. Change management and institutional reform for the better management of UF-NBS</p> <p>4. 为更好地管理UF-NBS而进行的管理更新和机构改革</p>
Content suggestions 内容建议				
Team				

Task T4.2 - Urban Forest as Nature-Based Solutions Tools Development (25 min) - 工具 (25分钟)			
OBJECTIVES-目标	FUNCTIONALITY-功能性	INTEGRATION-融合	
What are knowledge gaps of users (e.g. regarding certain challenges in your city) which can be filled by each tool?	What should the tool be able to deliver in terms of handling, functionality, or expected output?	How should the results look like in order the ensure a realistic uptake by key users and stakeholders and adoption into urban planning practice?	
可以填补工具开发用户的知识差距是什么 (例如关于城市面临的特定挑战)?	在工具、功能或预期输出方面, 该工具应该能够做什么?	为了确保核心用户和利益相关者能够实际接受并采用到城市规划实践中, 哪些工具的功能最容易被接受?	
UFBS情景工具 			
Global benchmarking tool 			

Task T4.4 - Field laboratories (10 min) 野外测试场所 (10分钟)	
<p>1-UF-NBS field laboratory meaning</p>	
<p>2- Areas of interest you would like to be tested?</p>	
<p>3- Criteria to select case studies to test the tool</p>	
<p>4- Specify the name of your city of interested in testing the tool</p>	<p>4-请输入您认为可用于测试UF-NBS工具的城市名称</p>
<p>European cities-欧洲城市</p>	

Task 5.3 Maintaining a webinar platform for knowledge exchange and upskilling (3 minutes)	
<p>Add here any content that you would like to see covered in the CLEARING HOUSE webinar series - the themes are prescribed and linked directly to task 4.3 (see titles above) but the content is not fixed</p>	
Task 5.5 Innovation roadmap (2 minutes)	
<p>UNEP/ENR kick-off</p> <p>UNEP strategy I</p> <p>Month 14</p>	<p>Results development</p> <p>Implementation plan of ENR</p> <p>Month 20</p>
<p>Stakeholder of CH results use</p> <p>Update of the explanation plan</p> <p>Month 26</p>	<p>Update of the IPB strategy II</p> <p>Final version of the explanation plan</p> <p>Month 48</p>